

GROUND EFFECT ON FAN FORCED RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

Ultra high by-pass ratio (UHBR) turbofan configurations are promising concepts to address the issue of aircraft fuel burn reduction. The large fan diameter and the small ground clearance of these configurations can lead to aerodynamic interaction with the ground during take-off phases. The objective of the work described in this paper is to investigate the ground effect on the forced response of a large civil fan operating near the ground under crosswind conditions. Under these conditions a vortex can form between the ground and the intake and can lead to possible failure due to high cycle fatigue. An initial validation of the 3D RANS approach has been carried out against experimental data on an academic intake. The numerical approach has been used to compute the flow field around the intake of a large civil turbofan with and without the ground. Both coupled and decoupled aeromechanical methods based on a structural linear behavior and U-RANS aerodynamic calculations have been used to estimate the forced response at the crossing of the 2nd bending mode (2F) and the 4th engine order. The levels of vibration obtained are then compared to experimental results. The ability to predict the level of response at the design stage allows for implementing design solutions preventing possible failure due to high cycle fatigue and reduces design margins.

INTRODUCTION

A vortex can form under certain conditions when the intake of an engine is situated near the ground surface. This vortex may stretch from the surface into the inlet causing significant flow distortions. The vortex becomes visible in a rainy or humid day because the moisture at its

core condenses. This ground vortex can lead to ingestion of loose debris [17] and excessive blade vibrations [5] [7]. This paper deals with the second point.

The mechanisms of inlet vortex formation have been a popular subject of research since the 1950s. It was quickly identified that a necessary requirement for vortex formation is the existence of a stagnation point on the ground plane [17]. De Siervi et al.[4] suggested that there might be two different mechanisms of inlet vortex generation. The first of these is the amplification of ambient vorticity as the vortex lines are stretched and drawn into the inlet under headwind conditions. The second mechanism is that an inlet vortex can arise in an upstream irrotational flow, for an inlet in crosswind, which does not require the presence of ambient vorticity. The parameters that can be used to characterize this phenomenon are the velocity ratio U_i/U_∞ of inlet velocity to ambient velocity, the ratio h/D_i of inlet height to inlet diameter [4][19]. More recently, Murphy [14] proposed a series of experimental studies involving the effect of ground clearance, yaw angles and intensity of incoming wind or even the ambient boundary layers size. Several authors have numerically replicated Murphy's configuration using Reynolds Average Navier Stokes (RANS) calculations in order to validate numerical approaches to characterize the inlet ground vortex [3][2][9][21]. The first section of this paper includes a validation section by comparing numerical results with the data obtained by Murphy [14]. The numerical approach is then used on a large civil turbofan. A comparison of distortion with and without ground is performed.

A frequent cause of turbomachinery blade failure is excessive resonant response. The standard method for dealing with this problem is to avoid resonant conditions using a Campbell diagram. Unfortunately, it is impossible to avoid all resonant conditions, especially during the take-

off phases where the ground vortex can appear. Previous studies from Green [7] and Di Mare et al. [5] showed that the ingested inlet ground vortex could lead to a large increase in the fan forced resonant response. During the last decades, several numerical approaches have been developed to predict forced response. A classification of these approaches can be found in literature [11]. The coupled approach consists in coupling the fluid and the structure at each time step. Although being the most representative approach, the coupled approach is very expensive due to the long time to converge to periodic state. For blade forced responses, the decoupled approach based on the superposition principle is often preferred because it is less computationally expensive and gives similar results compared to the coupled approach [10][18][13]. The second part of this paper consists in evaluating the vibration response of the fan blade of a large civil turbofan, due to cross wind distortion. Both decoupled and coupled approaches are used to compute blade vibration for the crossing corresponding to second bending mode and the fourth engine order. Numerical predictions are then compared to experimental results for both with and without ground cases.

NOMENCLATURE

A	aerodynamic stiffness matrix
B	aerodynamic damping matrix
h	distance to the ground
DC_{60}	distortion coefficient
D_i	inside diameter
D_l	highlight diameter
f	frequency
G_{af}	generalized aerodynamic forces = $\Phi^T F_{aero}$
P_{dyn}	dynamic pressure
P_T	total pressure
q	generalized coordinate
q^*	generalized coordinate amplitude
\hat{q}	complex generalized coordinate
U_i	velocity inside the intake
U_∞	cross-wind velocity
U^*	velocity ratio = U_i/U_∞
V_x	axial velocity
V_t	tangential velocity
α	swirl angle
β	modal mechanical damping matrix
Γ	circulation
γ	modal stiffness matrix
μ	modal mass matrix
Φ	modal base
ϕ	mode
ψ	generalized coordinate phase
ω	pulsation

INTAKE COMPUTATIONS

Validation on academic configuration

Experimental case

The experimental configuration chosen to validate the numerical method for predicting the distortion generated by ground vortex is the one studied by Murphy in [14]. The experiments were conducted in the Cranfield University low-speed wind tunnel which has a 2.4 m x 1.8 m working section. The intake model is axisymmetric and cylindrical in shape. The lip geometry is an ellipse with an aspect ratio of 2. The inner diameter D_i of the model equals 0.1 m. The fan is not included in the model, the mass-flow is provided by a vacuum tank situated outside the tunnel. The intake is equipped with total pressure rake ports situated at a distance of $0.7 D_i$ from the inlet plan. A PIV equipment is also installed in order to determine the velocity field at a plane parallel to the ground. Figure 1 illustrates the configuration and the two measured planes.

Figure 1: Experimental configuration of Murphy [X14]

Numerical setup

The three-dimensional flow field was predicted with elsA(ONERA-Airbus-Safran property)[1] based on the solution of the RANS equations for a compressible and ideal gas. Spatial discretisation was performed using AUSM+(P) scheme [12]. The turbulence model $k - \omega$ of Menter with SST correction is used. The overall computational domain consists in a rectangular prism with $25 D_l$ length and width and $12.5 D_l$ height. The diameter D_l represents the highlight diameter. The ground clearance is set at $h/D_l = 0.25$ where h represents the distance between the ground and the lower point of the highlight plane. A chimera approach with two parts is implemented to mesh this configuration. The geometry is axisymmetric however an azimuthal distribution is set in order to densify the zone where the vortex is likely to appear. The azimuthal distribution consists of 321 points. The first cell size of the intake is 1 mm and allows obtaining y^+ near unity. The intake mesh comprises 4.7 millions cells. The second part of the mesh consists of a cartesian mesh. In the zone where the vortex can appear, the cells have a volume of $2mm^3$. The first cell size at the ground is 10 mm resulting to y^+ near unity considering the wind velocities

studied. The background mesh comprises 3.9 million cells. The whole structured mesh comprises 8.6 million cells. A condition of adiabatic is applied on the ground and the intake. The upstream boundary is specified as a pressure inlet where the total pressure profile was chosen to produce the same boundary layer characteristics as the experiments. The downstream boundary implements a pressure outlet condition where the pressure is specified to deliver the required crosswind. The intake suction flow is also generated by a pressure outlet condition inside the duct. The relation between the pressure outlet and the mass flow is unknown a priori. An iterative procedure is necessary to find the experimental velocity ratio U^* defined as the ratio between the velocity in the intake U_i and the crosswind U_∞ , however this procedure can be expensive. In practice, the outlet pressure value is determined to get an intake Mach number near the one observed in the Murphy's study. The intensity of the crosswind is then changed to study the range of U^* evaluated by Murphy. Four velocity ratios are evaluated: U^* of 5.3, 7.4, 10.1 and 16.6. Symmetrical conditions were applied on the others domain limits.

Figure 2: Flow field topology ($U^* = 16.6$, $h/D_l = 0.25$, $M_l = 0.55$)

Results

The flow field topology is correctly evaluated by the numerical approach. A strong vortex starting from the ground is ingested into the intake (blue streamlines on Figure 2). This ground vortex is accompanied by a trailing vortex that can be separated into two parts. The first, represented by the red streamlines on Figure 2, is also ingested in the intake and can produce distortion close to the intake wall. The second part, illustrated by the black streamlines on Figure 2, is not ingested and swept away by the cross wind. This trailing vortex topology was also observed numerically by Zantopp [21]. The numerical and experimental total pressure fields in the fan plane are compared for two velocity ratios: $U^* \sim 10$ and $U^* \sim 5$. For the first one, the measures performed by Murphy and the CFD results are illustrated Figure 3. The position of the vortex is correctly predicted, the vortex is located near the wall of the intake and slightly off-centred in the direction of the incoming crosswind. The size of the low pressure zone is slightly over-estimated by the numerical study. The

total pressure drop at the vortex core is under-estimated, in fact the pressure ratio is near 0.75 for the experimental results and only 0.80 for the numeric ones. Results for the velocity ratio $U^* \sim 5$ are illustrated Figure 4. A pressure loss resulting from a lip separation is observed both in the experimental and numerical studies.

Figure 3: Total pressure in fan face for $U^* \sim 10$. Top: numerical results, bottom: experimental results.

Figure 4: Total pressure in fan face for $U^* \sim 5$. Top: numerical results, bottom: experimental results.

The position is also well captured by the numerical approach for this case. Despite the total pressure loss still being under-predicted, the evolution compared to the previous case ($U^* \sim 10$) which corresponds to an increase in wind intensity (i.e. decrease in U^*) is correctly predicted: the total pressure loss is more pronounced and the vortex position is more centred. Zantopp [21], who used a RANS approach on the same configuration, also observed an under-prediction of the level of total pressure loss at the vortex core. The pressure distortion was evaluated using the DC_{60} coefficient (Eq. (1)). It is defined as the difference between the average total pressure at the fan face \overline{P}_T and the minimum average total pressure in a 60° sector $P_{T,60}$, non-dimensionalised by the dynamic pressure P_{dyn} .

$$DC_{60} = \frac{\overline{P}_T - P_{T,60}}{P_{dyn}} \quad (1)$$

The evolution of DC_{60} against the velocity ratio is presented Figure 5 for both numerical and experimental studies. The results of Murphy show a slight increase of DC_{60} between $U^* = 18.3$ and $U^* = 7.3$ before a stronger increase until $U^* = 4.6$. The change of behaviour is linked to the presence of lip separation as illustrated Figure 4. Concerning the RANS results, DC_{60} is under-estimated for the three biggest U^* values. This observation is consistent with the study of total pressure field for $U^* \sim 10$ where the total pressure loss was underestimated by the numerical approach. Concerning $U^* = 5.3$, the DC_{60} is higher and seems well predicted by the numerical approach. As it is illustrated on Figure 4, this case presents a lip separation. The 60° sector with the minimal average total pressure is no longer only driven by the total pressure loss of the vortex but by the size and intensity of the lip separation. This configuration shows the limitation of this indicator to characterize the distortion associated to the ground vortex.

The strength of the vortex is characterized by the non-dimensionalised circulation Γ^* which is the circulation Γ non-dimensionalised by the diameter D_l and velocity at the fan plane U_i (Eq.(2)).

$$\Gamma^* = \frac{\Gamma}{D_l U_i} \quad (2)$$

The circulation was computed by integrating the outplane vorticity near the ground in a plane from a distance of $0,083D_l$ to the ground. The evolution of Γ^* against the velocity ratio U^* is presented Figure 6 for both numerical and experimental studies. The strength of the ground vortex increases when the velocity ratio decreases (ie when the wind intensity increases for a constant intake mass flow). This evolution is well captured by the numerical model and the numerical value of the circulation shows good agreement for U^* of 5.3, 7.4 and. 10.1. The circulation of the case of $U^* = 16.6$ is slightly over-predicted.

Figure 5: DC_{60} comparison between CFD results and experimental results from Murphy

Figure 6: Γ^* comparison between CFD results and experimental results from Murphy

In conclusion, the numerical approach allows reproducing the main characteristics of the flow field of an intake near a ground in crosswind conditions. The topology of the flow field is well captured and leads to correct estimation of the ground vortex position. Even an under prediction of the total pressure loss at the vortex core, the RANS approach provides good agreement in the vortex strength compared to the experimental data.

Application to an industrial turbofan: MASCOT 2

The MASCOT 2 configuration

MASCOT 2 is a Safran Aircraft Engines full-scale turbofan demonstrator for modern aero-engines. This demonstrator has been tested through a complete experimental campaign, including performance, acoustics, operability and cross-wind tests. It provides a valuable database to validate simulation models. In this paper we focus on the cross-wind tests where the fan blade vibrations were measured both with and without ground. During these tests, no information on the flow field around the intake or on the distortion inside the intake is available.

Numerical setup

The same numerical method and boundary conditions were used for the industrial configuration. Only the domain size and the meshing strategy have been modified. The domain was slightly smaller: length and height of $10 D_l$ and width of $20 D_l$. To avoid interpolation at the chimera interface, the inlet and ambient volume were meshed without using the chimera technique. This approach should not change the previous conclusions on the validity of the method. The distance between the ground and the intake corresponds to an h/D_l ratio around 0.35. Grid convergence study was performed. Several mesh refinements characterized by the azimuthal discretisation were evaluated: 240, 360, 480, 536 and 600 points in azimuth. The convergence of DC_{60} and Γ are reached for the mesh with a distribution of 536 points. A mesh without ground was also generated. The height of the mesh was doubled to approximately $20 D_l$ and a symmetric condition was applied on the lower limit of the domain for the mesh without ground. The same mesh refinement was kept. The velocity ratio U^* , resulting from the crosswind and the mass flow studied, is close to 13. Considering the value of U^* and h/D_l in this case, the ground presence implies a formation of a ground vortex ingested by the intake. The numerical model is depicted on Figure 7 where streamlines of ground vortex and trailing vortices are illustrated.

Figure 7: Flow field topology in MASCOT2 case.

Results

The total pressure distortions obtained inside the intake with and without ground are presented Figure 8. The total pressure loss induced by the ground vortex is easily visible in the lower part of the pressure field for the case with ground. The zone of pressure distortion is localized in a very confined space at high radius. Another total pressure distortion is present in both cases for high radius at the upper part. This distortion comes from the ingestion of the trailing vortex illustrated Figure 7.

In order to characterise the distortion induced by the ground vortex it is interesting to look at the swirl angle defined by Eq.(3). The swirl angle distortions for both with and without ground cases are presented Figure 9.

$$\alpha = \arctan\left(\frac{V_x}{V_t}\right) \quad (3)$$

Figure 8: Total pressure map. *Top: with ground, bottom: without ground.*

Figure 9: Swirl angle map. *Top: with ground, bottom: without ground.*

The azimuthal variation of the swirl angle gives an idea of the variation of the blade angles of attack during the rotation and therefore the variation of aerodynamic forces which will impact forced response. In the case with ground, the vortex leads to two large zones of swirl angle distortion: one near the shroud with positive angle and one for lower radius with negative swirl angle. Contrary to the total pressure distortion, the swirl distortion impacts a

large radial area. At the vortex core, where the total pressure drop is the highest, the swirl angle is very low, probably because tangential velocity is near zero in this region. We can also notice that in the case without ground, the swirl angle is not constant in the map as the total pressure is (see Figure 8). This distortion is due to the intake non-axisymmetry and the cross wind condition. In conclusion, for this industrial configuration, the ground vortex leads to a very localized total pressure drop and strong positive and negative swirl angles.

EVALUATION OF THE FAN FORCED RESPONSE

Numerical methodology

In this study, the behaviour of the structure is assumed to be linear. The blade displacement can be expressed in the modal base Φ with the generalized coordinates q .

$$u = \Phi q \quad (4)$$

The modal dynamical equation for the aeromechanical system is expressed with the modal mass matrix μ , modal mechanical damping matrix β , modal stiffness matrix γ and generalized aerodynamic forces G_{af} , which are the aerodynamic forces projected on the modal base, in Eq.(5).

$$\mu \ddot{q}(t) + \beta \dot{q}(t) + \gamma q(t) = G_{af}(t) \quad (5)$$

Structural modelling

The finite element structural model used is classically a single sector of disk and fan blade. A static computation is first made including centrifugal effects and static aerodynamic pressure. The shape and characteristics of the modes are obtained by a modal analysis including cyclic symmetrical conditions [8][20]. The complex mode shape obtained on the reference blade is recombined on the whole row using cyclic symmetrical properties. The full annulus complex mode is separated into two real modes ϕ' and ϕ'' as it is illustrated on Figure 10 for the second bending mode and the nodal diameter 4. These two real modes have the same frequency and the same generalized mass. The present study aims to compute the response at the 2F-4/rev crossing therefore the modal base can be reduced to only these two modes. The combination of these two real modes allows describing direct and indirect rotating waves. The mechanical damping β is neglected in this study.

Figure 10 : Tangential displacement of the 2F-4/rev modeshape. Left: ϕ' , right: ϕ''

Aerodynamic calculations

Aerodynamic calculations are performed using U-RANS modeling with elsA (ONERA-Airbus-SAFRAN property)[1]. Arbitrary Lagrangian–Eulerian formulation (ALE) is used to take into account the deformation of the mesh at each time step [16][6]. The Jameson scheme is used as spatial discretisation. The turbulence model $k - \omega$ of Menter with SST correction is used. The temporal discretisation is achieved by a GEAR scheme with 15 dual iterations. 720 times steps per revolution are performed. The model used for aerodynamic calculations includes the 18 fan blades, a splitter and only one OGV. The domain is illustrated in Figure 11 and contains more than 50 million cells. The secondary flow exit is controlled by a static pressure outlet and a radial equilibrium condition. Azimuthal averaged mixing condition is applied between the OGV and the fan. The primary flow exit is also controlled by outlet static pressure prescription using a radial equilibrium condition. A condition of injection is applied at the inlet. Total pressure, total enthalpy, velocity vector and turbulent variables are directly interpolated from the intake calculations presented in the previous section (with and without ground). For the 8 first cells the flow is resolved in the absolute frame before being resolved in the relative frame thanks to a sliding mesh condition (replaced by a mixing plane for steady initialization calculations). The mode shapes are interpolated onto the fan aerofoil surface in the CFD model. Only the two real mode shapes ϕ' and ϕ'' are embedded in this study because the forced response on the 2F-4/rev is driven by these modes.

Figure 11: CFD domain.

Decoupled approach

The decoupled approach is based on the superposition principle which consists in separating the generalized aerodynamic forces induced by the distortion, G_{af}^f , and the damping generalized aerodynamic forces induced by vibration, G_{af}^d , as it is illustrated Eq.(6).

$$\mu \ddot{q}(t) + \gamma q(t) = G_{af}^d(q, \dot{q}) + G_{af}^f(t) \quad (6)$$

The damping generalized aerodynamic forces are assumed linear with the displacement and the velocity.

This assumption is generally valid for turbomachinery blades which are of high density and stiffness and vibrate at low amplitudes. Finally, the displacement of the blades is described by the Eq. (7) where A is the aerodynamic stiffness matrix and B the aerodynamic damping matrix.

$$\mu \ddot{q}(t) + \gamma \dot{q}(t) = Aq(t) + B\dot{q}(t) + G_{af}^f(t) \quad (7)$$

By considering only the complex mode 2F with a nodal diameter of 4 (ϕ' and ϕ''), the system defined in Eq.(7) is reduced to only two real equations coupled by aerodynamic matrices A and B .

Usually, the excitation forces (G_{af}^f) and the aerodynamic response to motion (G_{af}^d) are evaluated through two individual CFD computations. The excitation forces G_{af}^f are estimated using a stage computation (distortion + fan) with the assumption of the blade-motion-independence. The aerodynamic matrices A and B are obtained by performing the computation in a clean flow (without the distortion) with a prescribed forced harmonic motion [13][18]. In this study a different approach has been used to estimate A, B and G_{af}^f . Two computations are made with the distortion and a prescribed harmonic motion. Such computation can be called 'twin computation'. The only difference between these two twin computations is the amplitude and the phase chosen for the prescribed harmonic motion. The analysis of the temporal generalized aerodynamic forces allows to extract A and B and therefore to build G_{af}^f . The interest of this approach is to keep the same numerical method for both computations and therefore avoid modelling issues due to modification of boundary conditions. Moreover, it simplifies the set up compared to the classical approach that requires two different setups. In order to explain the process, we will focus on single degrees of freedom but it is easily transposable to the two real modes case resulting of the cyclic symmetry properties. Two computations, indexed by 1 and 2, with two prescribed motion with an amplitude of q^* , a phase ψ and the same pulsation ω (which is 4 times the pulsation of the rotating pulsation in a case of a 4/rev crossing) are considered. These two prescribed motion are expressed in Eq. (8).

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= q_1^* \cos(\omega t + \psi_1) \\ q_2 &= q_2^* \cos(\omega t + \psi_2) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

An example of the evolution of the generalized aerodynamic force mode ϕ' is illustrated Figure 12 for two different twin computations with different amplitude of prescribed motion. Thanks to superposition and linear assumptions, the generalized aerodynamic forces can be written as a function of aerodynamic matrix and generalized aerodynamic forces due to the distortion, as shown in Eq.(9).

$$\begin{aligned} G_{af,1} &= Aq_1^* \cos(\omega t + \psi_1) - \omega Bq_1^* \sin(\omega t + \psi_1) + G_{af}^f \\ G_{af,2} &= Aq_2^* \cos(\omega t + \psi_2) - \omega Bq_2^* \sin(\omega t + \psi_2) + G_{af}^f \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

A Fourier analysis of the difference between the two G_{af} is then carried out and leads to Eq. (10) where Re represents the real part and Im the imaginary part.

$$\frac{2}{T} \int_0^T (G_{af,1} - G_{af,2}) e^{-j\omega t} dt = Re + j Im \quad (10)$$

Then, by replacing $G_{af,1}$ and $G_{af,2}$ by their expression in Eq. (9), the Fourier analysis can be written as shown in Eq. (11).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T (G_{af,1} - G_{af,2}) e^{-j\omega t} dt = \\ A(q_1^* \cos \psi_1 - q_2^* \cos \psi_2) + \omega B (q_2^* \sin \psi_2 - q_1^* \sin \psi_1) + \\ j[A(q_1^* \sin \psi_1 - q_2^* \sin \psi_2) + \omega B (q_1^* \cos \psi_1 - q_2^* \cos \psi_2)] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The identification of Re and Im and the real and imaginary part of Eq. 11 leads to a 2x2 system where the unknown are A and B (which are scalar in the one degree of freedom case). Once the system resolved, the generalized aerodynamic forces induced by the distortion G_{af}^f are obtained by subtracting the generalized aerodynamic forces due to motion to the total generalized aerodynamic forces (see Eq.(9)). In the case of the two real modes ϕ' and ϕ'' from the cyclic symmetries formulation, two twin computations are made by imposing motion on the mode ϕ' . In view of the properties of aerodynamic matrices A and B due to cyclic symmetry properties, the Fourier analysis leads to a 4x4 system allowing the determination of the aerodynamic matrices. In the same way, the generalized aerodynamic forces due to distortion $G_{af}^f = [G_{af}^{f'}, G_{af}^{f''}]^T$ are obtained by subtracting the part due to motion to the total generalized aerodynamic forces (see Eq. (9)).

Figure 12: Example of evolution generalized aerodynamic forces G'_{af} for two twin computations.

At a resonance condition, the displacement and therefore the generalized coordinates are assumed harmonic with a pulsation ω . The generalized coordinate can be written thanks to the complex number \hat{q}' and \hat{q}'' as illustrated in Eq. (12).

$$q = [\hat{q}' e^{j\omega t}, \hat{q}'' e^{j\omega t}]^T \quad (12)$$

The system of the Eq. (7) can thus be written as shown in Eq. (13).

$$(\gamma - A - \omega^2 \mu - j\omega B) \begin{bmatrix} \hat{q}' \\ \hat{q}'' \end{bmatrix}^T = \frac{2}{T} \int_0^T \begin{bmatrix} G_{af}' \\ G_{af}'' \end{bmatrix}^T e^{-j\omega t} dt \quad (13)$$

The complex generalized coordinates \hat{q}' and \hat{q}'' are then obtained by inverting the system. Eq. (13) is valid only at the frequency computed in twin calculations. However, for a range of frequencies close to this frequency, the aerodynamic behaviour is assumed to stay the same. In the context of steady excitation in the absolute frame, the resolution leads to the same amplitude and a 90° phase-shift for the modes ϕ' and ϕ'' , which describes an indirect rotating wave in the relative frame.

Coupled approach

The coupled approach consists in directly solving the dynamical system shown in Eq. (14) where W represents the fluid state.

$$\mu \ddot{q}(t) + \gamma q(t) = G_{af}(W(q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q})) \quad (14)$$

In elsA (ONERA-Airbus-Safran property), solving this coupled problem requires iterating between fluid resolution and structural resolution. The algorithm chosen is illustrated for one time step **Figure 13**. The four steps illustrated are the following:

- 1- Mesh deformation.
- 2- Fluid resolution: this step is described in previous paragraph *aerodynamic calculations*.
- 3- G_{af} computations.
- 4- Structure resolution: this step is achieved with a 2nd order Newmark scheme.

Figure 13: Coupled approach algorithm.

These for 4 steps are repeated n_{loop} times until convergence for the same time step (in practise, only 3 loops are necessary) before switching to the next time step. This approach allows getting rid of superposition and linear aerodynamic assumptions; however such computation can be very expensive because it requires time to reach the periodic state. Two rotating speeds values close to the crossing rotating speed have been calculated with this approach for the ground case, i.e. with an inlet

distortion map coming from a previous intake calculation including ground.

Figure 14: Top: Generalized coordinate q' time evolution comparison between coupled and decoupled approach. Bottom: zoom on the last revolution.

In order to compare coupled and decoupled approaches in the time domain, the decoupled equation (Eq. (7)) is also solved with the same Newmark scheme as the one used for coupled case. The results are presented **Figure 14**. At the top, the evolution of the generalized coordinate q' are compared between coupled and decoupled approaches. More than 13 revolutions are needed to reach the periodic state. Small differences are visible in the first revolutions due to the aerodynamic transient induced by initialisation of the stationary field in the coupled case (in the decoupled case, the generalized aerodynamic forces induced by the excitation are extracted from twin computations in a periodic state, after this aerodynamic transient). After this part, the generalized coordinates of the two approaches are very close. The second figure, which is a zoom one the last revolution, confirms that the coupled and decoupled approaches lead to very close amplitude and phase, for both generalized coordinates q' and q'' . The levels predicted by the coupled approach are slightly higher than the ones predicted by the decoupled approach but the relative difference is near 2%. The assumption on superposition and linear aerodynamic behaviour are therefore validated in this configuration. In conclusion, it does not seem necessary to run coupled approach in this ground vortex ingestion case.

Experimental cross-wind study

Cross-wind tests consist in slow increase in a rotating speed from idle speed to the maximum speed of the engine. Four fan blades are instrumented with strain gauges during cross-wind study of MASCOT2 campaign test. The gauges used are mainly sensitive to the second bending mode. In order to extract the component induced by the crossing 2F-4/rev in the strain gauge measurements, the 4th engine order signal is selected thanks to a sliding Fourier transformation. The measured data are then converted into generalized coordinate levels thanks to the comparison with the normalized stress extracted during the modal analysis.

Results

The numerical predictions of the generalized coordinate amplitude by the coupled and decoupled approaches are compared to the experimental results on Figure 15. Both with and without ground cases are illustrated. Two rotating speed are evaluated by the coupled approach. As shown in the previous section, there is a very good agreement between the decoupled and the coupled approaches: the two coupled approach results are almost superimposed on the decoupled curve. The experimental results show that the distortion produced by the vortex occurrence implies a maximum response three times stronger than the natural distortion associated only with cross wind. This strong effect of the vortex was already pointed out in [5][7]. The ratio between with and without ground cases is well captured by the numerical predictions even if the maximum response is slightly overestimated. In the ground case, numerical predictions lead to a tighter curve than the experimental one which indicates that the damping is probably under-predicted.

Figure 15: Forced response for the 2F-4/rev crossing with and without ground, numerical predictions against experimental results

CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

An initial validation of the computational model used for characterizing the inlet vortex has been carried out against experimental data concerning an academic intake test case from the existing literature. The numerical

approach has allowed reproducing the main characteristics of the flow field occurring at an intake near ground in crosswind conditions. The topology of the flow field was well captured and simulations have led to a correct estimation of the ground vortex position. Even if the total pressure loss in the vortex core was under-predicted, the RANS approach has provided good agreement in the vortex circulation compared to the experimental data. This numerical approach has been used on the full-scale turbofan demonstrator MASCOT2. The distortion induced by the ground vortex has been characterized by comparing total pressure and swirl angle maps obtained for configurations with and without ground. The ground vortex is responsible for a total pressure loss confined at its core and strong positive and negative swirl angles impacting a large radial area.

Both decoupled and coupled approaches have been used to estimate fan forced response on the MASCOT2 2F-4/rev crossing. These approaches are based on aerodynamic U-RANS calculations and linear structural behaviour. The decoupled approach, based on superposition principle and linear aerodynamic behaviour, was used with two twin calculations with different prescribed harmonic motion. The aerodynamic excitation forces due to distortion and the aerodynamic response due to blade motion are then obtained through the analysis of generalized aerodynamic forces from the two twin calculations. The coupled approach is based on temporal integration for which the fluid and the structure are solved iteratively until convergence for each time step. This approach is much more time consuming than the decoupled one. Both approaches have led to very close results which validates the assumptions of superposition and linear aerodynamic behaviour used in the decoupled approach. The numerical predictions of fan forced response were then compared to experimental results and showed a good agreement for both with and without ground cases. The increase of the vibration level induced by the ground vortex was well captured by the numerical approach. However, the maximum vibration levels were slightly overestimated by the numerical approach. The methodology described in this paper is able to evaluate the level of response due to complex excitation at the design stage. This allows design solutions to be implemented in order to prevent possible failure due to high cycle fatigue.

The next step will consist in taking into account the non-linear behaviour of the structure coming from blade-disk contact [15]. Furthermore, an unsteady calculation including intake, ground and fan will be addressed in order to get rid of the boundary injection condition in fan calculations. This computation will be able to capture the unsteady ground vortex nature and a potential aerodynamic coupling between the fan and the ground vortex. Another aspect will consist in developing an analytical model allowing fast evaluations of forced response based on distortion maps. Such models could be easily integrated in design process.

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